

Transformation of Jember Regency, East Java, Indonesia to Become as a MICE Industry in Collaboration with Among Natural and Cultural Advantages

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ABSTRACT: One of the sectors in tourism that is currently the main focus is Meeting, Incentive, Conference, Exhibition (MICE). MICE relates to the organization of business meetings, incentive programs organized by companies, large-scale meetings involving participants from various places, exhibitions, and many more. MICE contributes greatly to the economic growth of a region by bringing in revenue streams from event participants, as well as driving consumption in the local tourism sector, such as accommodation, restaurants and transportation. Jember Regency, located in East Java Province, has the potential to develop a promising MICE sector. Jember has a number of advantages to attract attention as a MICE destination and is one of the largest regencies in East Java with a variety of natural, cultural and creative economy tourism potential. Jember's natural beauty, from beautiful beaches such as Papuma Beach to verdant mountains such as Mount Argopuro, provides an enchanting backdrop for many MICE events. Cultural treasures, such as the internationally renowned Labako Dance and Jember Fashion Carnaval, add to the appeal.

KEYWORDS: Jember Regency, MICE Industry, Tourism Potential.

INTRODUCTION

Jember Regency in East Java Province is increasingly showing its potential as a Meeting, Incentive, Convention, and Exhibition (MICE) tourism center. Jember offers extraordinary natural beauty as it has many natural resources, ranging from beautiful beaches to charming green mountains. In addition, unique local cultures, such as the Labako Dance and the world-famous Jember Fashion Carnaval Festival, attract tourists and MICE businesses (Helpiastuti, 2018).

Improved infrastructure, such as modern conference halls and adequate accommodation facilities, has helped Jember develop into a MICE tourism destination. In addition, the local government is working to promote Jember through various international events and improve transportation convenience by building better transportation routes. Jember has many natural and cultural advantages as well as adequate infrastructure that make it an ideal place for MICE activities. The city offers a unique and memorable experience for every visitor (Abdillah et al., 2023).

DISCUSSION

Jember Regency has outstanding natural and cultural advantages, as well as an increasingly developed infrastructure, which is driving its transformation into a MICE (Meeting, Incentive, Convention, and Exhibition) tourism area. The natural landscape of Jember Regency is stunning, ranging from beautiful beaches such as Papuma Beach and Watu Ulo Beach to green and cool mountains such as Mount Argopuro. Its extraordinary beauty provides an ideal backdrop for a variety of MICE events, offering a unique experience that combines business and entertainment activities (Vicy Andriany, 2021).

Jember's main attraction is its cultural excellence. Local traditions, such as the Labako Dance, which depicts the life of tobacco farmer, and the Jember Fashion Carnaval, a world-renowned street fashion event, demonstrate the rich culture that can be incorporated into MICE events. The Jember Fashion Carnaval Festival has attracted worldwide attention and become one of

Jember's cultural icons that can be used to raise the city's profile as MICE destination. This transformation prioritizes infrastructure development (Damanik et al., 2018).

The local government has endeavored to improve supporting facilities, including meeting venues, hotels and resorts. The renovation and expansion of Notohadinegoro Airport, which now serves flights from various cities in Indonesia, making it easier for MICE participants from different regions, is a clear example. In addition, the construction of a new highway in Jember will ease access to various tourist attractions and MICE centers. This new infrastructure increases mobility and improves convenience (Damanik et al., 2018).

The Jember Regency's Government is actively promoting the MICE destination by holding tourism exhibitions and marketing campaigns, as well as working with travel agents and event organizers. The aim of these initiatives is to strengthen Jember's position as a MICE hub and attract more national and international events to it. Jember Regency has great potential to become a leading MICE destination in Indonesia if its natural advantages, cultural richness, and infrastructure work well. With this transformation, Jember will become an attractive tourist city and drive the growth of local economic (Damanik et al., 2018).

CONCLUSION

Jember Regency has developed into a MICE tourism center thanks to combination of natural advantages, cultural richness, and adequate infrastructure. The main attractions are the beauty of the beaches and mountains, as well as local traditions, such as the Labako Dance and Jember Fashion Carnaval. Jember's competitiveness is strengthened by the development of new infrastructure, such as modern conference halls and improved accessibility through Notohadinegoro Airport. International exposure is increasing with active local government promotion. Jember has enormous potential, which will drive local economic growth and provide visitors with memorable experiences.

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